

Political Parallelism and Voters' Choice of Candidates in Elections

David Babatunde Ojeifo

Department of Mass communication,
University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria
davidojeifo15@gmail.com; +2347065176038

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Abstract

This study critically examined political parallelism and voters' choice of candidates in elections, drawing attention to how partisan alignments between media institutions and political actors shape electoral decision-making in Nigeria. Despite growing scholarly interest in media influence on political communication, the specific concept of political parallelism has received limited attention within Nigerian academia. Most existing literature focused on agenda setting, framing or media bias in general, without clearly theorising how structural or ideological media alignments influence voters' choices. This conceptual gap necessitated a focused analysis of political parallelism and its implications for electoral behaviour. Anchored on the political parallelism theory, the researchers adopted a qualitative, literature-based methodology. It drew from verified empirical studies and theoretical sources to establish how ownership structures, editorial loyalties and partisan framing practices distort the informational environment during elections. It argued that such distortion narrows the democratic space by undermining voters' access to balanced political discourse and reinforcing ethno-political loyalties. The study showed that politically-aligned media content often amplifies dominant narratives, excluding dissenting views and manipulates electoral perceptions thereby strongly influencing voters' choices, irrespective of objective narratives, candidates' manifestoes or portfolios. It concluded that political parallelism, if unaddressed, will continue to compromise electoral credibility and deepen political polarisation. To counteract these effects, the paper recommended regulatory reforms that promote editorial independence, enforcement of professional media ethics and investment in media literacy programmes to equip citizens with critical interpretive skills.

Keywords: Political Parallelism, Media Ownership, Voter Behaviour, Editorial Bias, Nigerian Elections

Introduction

Elections stand as the most recognisable symbol of democratic expression. However, the credibility of that expression often depends less on the voting itself and more on the nature of the information environment that precedes it. Across many democracies and especially in Nigeria, the media play an instrumental role in shaping how voters understand politics. Citizens do not form electoral opinions in isolation; they engage with narratives shaped by the media, which influences how political options are perceived and interpreted.

Over time, political parallelism has become a visible feature of Nigeria's electoral culture. Rather than serving as neutral platforms, many media outlets actively participate in influencing voter perception through editorial selection, framing choices, and narrative shaping. This is largely driven by ownership structures that are closely linked to political elites. Those in government or with political ambitions often control or fund media organisations, using them to promote partisan interests (Akinfeleye, 2019). The consequences of such alignments are significant for democratic engagement; especially when media organisations are seen as lacking independence, public trust in their content declines. Ojebode & Adegbola (2021) maintained that media bias weakens the electorate's ability to engage critically with political information, fostering polarisation and encouraging voters to rely on sentiment rather than informed reasoning. Uche (2016) observed that media organisations in Nigeria frequently reflect ethnic and regional loyalties, especially during elections, rather than promoting a collective national identity. These concerns have been intensified by the rise of digital media. Online platforms have expanded access to political discourse but have also increased the speed and volume of biased or misleading content. Political actors take advantage of these tools to circulate partisan messages and discredit opposition voices, making it more difficult for voters to distinguish facts from propaganda (Ojebode & Adegbola, 2021).

Audience engagement with media is shaped by personal and social factors. People often seek information that confirms their existing beliefs. As Volkmer (2018) noted, this tendency can lead to echo chambers that limit exposure to diverse viewpoints, reducing opportunities for democratic reflection. Rather than challenging their own assumptions, voters may consume only content that aligns with their preferences, reinforcing divisions.

The persistence of political parallelism is also linked to weak regulatory oversight. Institutions such as the Nigerian Broadcasting Commission and the Nigerian Press Council struggle to enforce ethical standards, especially when dealing with politically connected media proprietors. According to Akinfeleye (2019), the failure of regulation allows biased reporting to thrive, often unchecked.

Nigeria's media have long been connected with political power. From the era of colonial resistance to periods of military rule, the press has served as both a platform for political advocacy and a battleground for influence. Historical figures like Earnest Ikoli used newspapers such as the *Nigerian Daily* and the *Daily Telegraph* not just to inform, but also to promote political goals (Obaze & Ojo, 2011). The *Tribune* newspaper's early alignment with regional political groups illustrates that political influence over media is a longstanding concern.

Today, many outlets continue to provide disproportionate coverage to select candidates while marginalising others. Hiebert, Ungurait & Bohn (1988) explained that editorial bias, often tied to ownership, could result in omission, distortion or outright suppression of alternative views. This restricts the diversity of political voices that voters can engage with and undermines the media's democratic function. It is against this backdrop that the position paper is presented.

The availability of fair and balanced information is vital for voters to make informed decisions. Yet political parallelism continues to distort how political choices are

framed and communicated. As a result, electoral decisions are often shaped more by curated images and persuasive messaging than by impartial scrutiny of competing ideas. While political pluralism in the media can reflect societal diversity, its value is lost when professional norms are ignored and media institutions become instruments of political mobilisation.

Statement of the Problem

Political parallelism is now a recurring feature of Nigeria's media landscape, yet its electoral implications remain insufficiently examined in local academic literature. Most political communication studies in Nigeria have focused on agenda setting, framing and media influence, with little attention given to how media affiliations shape electoral outcomes. Even when partisanship is acknowledged, it is rarely analysed using the concept of political parallelism, leaving a significant gap in understanding how voters process politically aligned media messages. As Hallin & Mancini (2004) asserted, political parallelism provides a robust framework for analysing the media-politics nexus, but it remains underapplied in Nigerian research.

Voters today face increasing exposure to partisan narratives across both traditional and digital media. Stories are often framed to support preferred candidates, while dissenting views are ignored or undermined. Despite this reality, there is limited empirical research on how Nigerian voters respond to such media environments. Volkmer (2018) warned of media-driven polarisation in transitional democracies, yet Nigerian scholars have scarcely applied this to local electoral discourse.

This research gap hampers efforts to understand media influence beyond broad claims of bias. Without systematic academic engagement, political parallelism remains vague and poorly theorised, making it difficult to guide policy or promote media literacy. This position paper addresses that gap. By focusing on political parallelism in Nigeria's electoral context, it highlights how partisan media shape candidate perception, influence political narratives and affect democratic participation.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on political parallelism theory, which provides a compelling lens through which to examine the relationship between media content and voter behaviour, particularly within politically charged electoral environments. This theory emerged from comparative media systems research, most notably advanced by Hallin & Mancini (2004), who described political parallelism as the extent to which media systems reflect the political divisions, ideologies, and affiliations of the broader political environment in which they operate.

At its core, the theory posits that media institutions do not merely report political events, but actively participate in the reproduction of political ideologies and partisanship through their structures, editorial choices, and ownership dynamics. Media organisations, especially those aligned with political parties or influential politicians, often project selective interpretations of political developments, thereby shaping how audiences perceive candidates and issues. This alignment is not always explicit; it may take the

form of recurring editorial slants, differential coverage intensity, or subtle framing techniques designed to elevate some candidates while marginalising others.

In societies where political parallelism is pronounced, the electorate's access to objective political information becomes compromised. Voters are more likely to encounter content that reinforces existing political loyalties, which in turn affects their decision-making processes. The theory helps to explain why audiences may trust partisan media despite their bias, as such platforms offer narratives that resonate with group identities, ideological leanings or regional affiliations.

In the Nigerian context, the political parallelism theory is especially relevant given the widespread ownership of media outlets by politically connected individuals and the prevalence of editorial content that aligns with specific parties or candidates. These conditions make it difficult for voters to encounter diverse or balanced perspectives, which are essential for reflective democratic participation. As political communication increasingly mirrors the ideological contours of the media space, voter choice is shaped not only by policy positions or candidate profiles, but also by the partisan framing through which such information is received.

This theory offers a valuable foundation for analysing the impact of politically aligned media on voter behaviour, particularly in emerging democracies where electoral competition is fierce, and information environments are often polarised. By anchoring this position paper in the Political Parallelism Theory, the analysis is better equipped to interrogate how media partisanship influences voter perceptions and shapes electoral decisions in ways that may both reflect and reproduce existing political divisions.

Conceptual Review of Political Parallelism

Political parallelism refers to the degree to which media organisations reflect political alignments in their operations, editorial content, and institutional structure. Hallin & Mancini (2004) conceptualised the term as the extent to which the media system mirrors the political party system in a given society. This alignment can manifest through formal connections between media owners and political actors, consistent support for particular ideologies or selective coverage that favours specific political positions.

Strömbäck & Esser (2019) explained that political parallelism operates not only at the level of media ownership but also in the journalistic routines that reproduce partisan interests. In such settings, the media serve as extensions of political agendas rather than as neutral information sources. Waisbord (2018) affirmed that in societies with fragile media independence, political parallelism becomes a mechanism through which media institutions serve elite interests, undermining their public accountability function.

In transitional democracies like Nigeria, Olorunnisola & Adegoke (2020) observed that political allegiances in media organisations are shaped by proprietorial links to politicians, which affects editorial direction and reportage. The concept is useful for assessing the structural entanglement of media institutions with political processes, especially in the context of electoral communication.

Political parallelism may also be reinforced by cultural, ethnic, and regional loyalties that shape editorial judgment and audience expectations. In multi-ethnic

societies, media outlets may cater to the preferences of particular identity groups, not only to secure audience loyalty but also to align with the ideological orientation of political sponsors. This dynamic can blur the boundaries between journalism and propaganda, especially during election periods when the stakes are high. Comparative research from El-Issawi (2016) and Richter (2020) supported this view by showing how identity politics in transitional societies such as Libya and Egypt contributes to the replication of political cleavages in the media system. These patterns mirror the Nigerian situation where media content often reflects political divides rather than unifying civic values.

Understanding Voter Behaviour

Voter behaviour encompasses the attitudes, beliefs and decision-making patterns of individuals as they engage with political communication and make electoral choices. It includes how voters receive and process information, evaluate candidates and parties and eventually translate media messages into electoral action. Uwalaka & Nwala (2021) defined voter behaviour as the cumulative result of long-term exposure to political messaging, shaped by personal identity, political knowledge and media influence.

Kulachai, Lerdtomornsakul & Homyamyen (2023) asserted that voter behaviour is shaped as much by socio-cultural factors as by issue-based campaigns. Ethnic, religious and regional affiliations play a decisive role in shaping political preferences, with many voters prioritising identity over ideology. This reflects a layered process in which media influence is mediated by social history and group loyalties.

The increasing penetration of digital platforms has added new dimensions to voter behaviour, especially among youth population. Arowolo & Ogande (2024) examined how social media use during the 2023 general elections enabled real-time political mobilisation, dissemination of campaign materials and interactive discussions. They also noted that digital engagement does not always lead to physical turnout at polling stations. Obiorah & Okafor (2023) similarly observe that online exposure may raise awareness but is often insufficient to alter voter decisions where entrenched political allegiances dominate.

These perspectives suggest that voter behaviour is not a direct response to media messages but is influenced by the intersection of media content, identity affiliations, political history, and broader structural realities. In environments marked by political parallelism, this interplay becomes even more complex, as voters interpret information through partisan lenses that both inform and limit their electoral choices.

Nigeria Election Reportage

Nigeria elections refer to the series of democratic exercises conducted to select public office holders at the federal, state, and local levels. Since the transition to civilian rule in 1999, elections have become a recurring feature of the country's democratic process. These elections, especially at the presidential level, are characterised by intense competition, significant media attention, and growing voter engagement.

Akinfeleye (2019) noted that the Nigerian media have played a pivotal role in electioneering and political mobilisation. However, their effectiveness has been constrained by editorial biases, partisanship, and ownership structures that favour political actors. Ojebode & Adegbola (2021) cautioned that this undermines public trust in the media and compromises the legitimacy of the electoral process. Uche (2016) observed that many Nigerian media organisations are influenced by regional or ethnic loyalties, and this has continued to shape electoral reporting. Such biases often affect the objectivity of political communication and intensify societal divisions during election periods. Instead of offering diverse and balanced viewpoints, media coverage tends to reflect the preferences of owners, sponsors or dominant political interests.

Digital technologies have significantly transformed the communication environment of Nigerian elections. Politicians increasingly use social media platforms to connect with voters, circulate campaign messages, and shape public narratives. Arowolo & Ogande (2024) explain that while these platforms enhance participation, they also provide avenues for spreading disinformation and political propaganda, which can mislead voters and distort campaign discourse. Regulatory oversight remains weak. Agencies such as the Independent National Electoral Commission and the Nigerian Broadcasting Commission struggle to ensure equitable media representation and enforce ethical standards during elections. Olorunnisola & Adegoke (2020) argued that the absence of strict regulation permits partisan media to flourish, further entrenching political parallelism and complicating the democratic process.

Nigeria elections, therefore, offer a rich context for evaluating the role of media in democratic development. The interaction of ownership influence, political partisanship and identity politics within the media environment shapes how information is presented to voters and how they respond during elections. These dynamics underscore the need for deeper scholarly engagement with concepts like political parallelism in understanding electoral behaviour.

Media Engagement and Political Participation

The role of media engagement in strengthening democratic participation has been consistently emphasised in political communication literature. Access to political information through newspapers, radio, television and digital platforms equips citizens with the knowledge and confidence to participate in elections and civic life. Fasola & Oyadeyi (2021) argued that individuals who are regularly exposed to political content are more inclined to see political participation as a civic obligation. Such exposure improves awareness and nurtures a sense of responsibility among voters.

However, access to political media in Nigeria is not uniform. Mustapha & Lasisi (2017) highlighted that rural populations are frequently marginalised in the flow of information due to infrastructural limitations. Consequently, disparities in media access result in unequal exposure to political discourse and differences in participatory engagement. The digital divide persists, despite the rapid expansion of online media platforms. The advent of social media has significantly reshaped political engagement, especially among young voters. Akinyetun (2021) noted that digital platforms serve as

spaces for political mobilisation, grassroots advocacy, and real-time engagement with election narratives. Citizens are no longer passive recipients of news but active participants in shaping political discussions. This was particularly evident in youth-led movements that influenced democratic reforms. Anajama (2018) cite the “Not Too Young to Run” campaign as an example of how digital engagement can lead to tangible policy outcomes.

Nonetheless, the same platforms that foster mobilisation also contribute to challenges in political participation. The proliferation of misinformation, clickbait content and biased reporting weakens public trust. Santas, Oputa & Igyuve (2025) found that exposure to such distorted narratives often breeds cynicism and discourages civic involvement. Inobemhe, Ja’afaru & Garba (2024) further argue that misinformation may have an alienating effect on voters, particularly during electoral cycles.

Media literacy has thus emerged as a necessary tool for promoting meaningful engagement (Ojeifo, Egharevba & Asemah, 2024). Similarly, Ogwezzy-Ndisika & Akinreti (2017) also underscored the relevance of alternative platforms such as community radio in amplifying local voices and improving access to political information, particularly in underserved areas.

Media Bias and Political Parallelism

Media bias and political parallelism are persistent and deeply embedded features of Nigeria’s media landscape. Media bias refers to the tendency of news organisations to favour certain political actors through selective reporting, editorial framing or narrative control. Political parallelism, in contrast, captures the broader institutional alignment between media outlets and political interests, particularly in ownership structures and editorial direction (Lawal & Ibrahim, 2019).

In Nigeria, media institutions are frequently aligned with political actors, either through direct ownership or ideological affiliation. Ojebuyi, Ekanem & Chibuwe (2023) noted that editorial control is often influenced by political loyalty, which undermines the principle of impartial reporting. Consequently, media houses function as partisan platforms, shaping narratives to support preferred candidates while marginalising opposition voices.

Framing practices further deepen political bias. Adisa, Ahmad & Mustapha (2018) found that newspapers regularly apply frames that assign blame or inflate urgency depending on the political context. Such framing significantly influences how readers perceive political actors and electoral issues. Popoola & Kolawole (2019) explained that consequence and human-interest frames often attract public empathy, while political strategy frames tend to provoke scepticism.

Sensational headlines and emotionally charged language are additional tools used to reinforce political preferences. Santas, Oputa & Igyuve (2023) documented how Nigerian media, particularly during elections, amplify rhetoric that legitimises allied candidates while undermining political opponents. Adama & Okeke, (2024) cautioned that even newer media houses replicate these practices, suggesting that partisanship has become institutionalised across the sector.

The independence of journalists is also severely compromised. Adeyanju & Alabi (2021) reported that editorial decisions in politically aligned newsrooms are often dictated by proprietors, leaving little room for investigative or critical journalism. The result is a weakened media system that fails to serve its democratic role.

Digital media have complicated the situation further. Inobemhe, Ja'afaru & Garba (2024) highlighted that political actors exploit digital channels to spread ideologically consistent narratives that reinforce partisan identities. This blurs the line between journalism and propaganda, leaving voters exposed to unverified or one-sided information in the heat of electoral contests.

Overall, the entrenchment of political parallelism and bias within Nigeria's media ecosystem limits the spectrum of political choices available to voters. It compromises the principle of informed choice and promotes selective exposure, polarisation and echo chamber effects.

Media Influence on Political Beliefs and Electoral Choices

The mass media have a long-standing influence on how citizens form political opinions, interpret information and choose candidates. Repetition of specific narratives gradually builds public attitudes toward political actors and institutions. Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam Uwaoma (2017) argued that constant exposure to issues such as corruption or incompetence can lead to entrenched public distrust. Over time, these narratives shape how voters define political integrity and competence.

Asemah, Kente & Nkwam- Uwaoma, A. O. A. (2019) observed that the prolonged circulation of negative political content creates a climate of suspicion around governance. As audiences internalise these portrayals, it fosters disillusionment and sometimes apathy toward the electoral process. According to Asemah, Ekhareafu & Olaniran (2020), this is further intensified by confirmation bias, where audiences seek only information that validates their existing views.

In digital media environments, algorithmic filters reinforce this behaviour by curating content that reflects users' preferences. This creates echo chambers where divergent perspectives are rarely encountered. Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam Uwaoma (2017) found that during election periods, media coverage often focuses on violence and fraud, thereby shifting public attention away from substantive policy debates.

Framing remains a powerful technique through which media shape political attitudes. Asemah & Nwaoboli (2022) revealed that selective amplification of party narratives through strategic framing influences voters' emotional alignment with particular candidates. In this way, media become not just conveyors of information but architects of political preference.

Asemah, Nwaoboli & Nwoko (2022) further documented that while online media platforms enabled civic expression during movements like #EndSARS, they also served as vehicles for misinformation. Their research suggests that such dual use contributes to conflicting belief systems within the electorate, as engagement may occur alongside manipulation.

Finally, the role of digital opinion leaders and community influencers has become increasingly significant. These intermediaries contextualise political information and transmit it to niche audiences through both digital and traditional platforms. As observed by Asemah, Nwaoboli & Nwoko (2022), these figures shape political orientation in ways that often reinforce communal biases rather than promote national consensus. Thus, media influence on political beliefs and voting choices is profound and multidimensional. In contexts like Nigeria, where political parallelism pervades both institutional and content levels, the media do not merely inform voters; they also condition how choices are perceived and justified.

Review of Empirical Studies

Umoro, Ogunyemi & Enabunene (2022) conducted a study titled *Newspaper Framing of Candidates in the 2020 Edo Governorship Election and its Influence on Voters' Choice of Candidates*, published in the *GVU Journal of Communication Studies*. The study investigated how major candidates in the 2020 Edo State governorship election were portrayed by newspapers and how this portrayal influenced voters' decisions. Grounded in the framing theory, the study employed both survey and content analysis methods to collect data.

Findings showed that media framing significantly shaped voters' choices, with many respondents affirming that their voting decisions were influenced by how candidates were represented in the media. The portrayal of candidates, whether favourable or unfavourable, contributed to shaping public perception and preferences. This underscores the influential role of editorial emphasis and narrative construction in electoral behaviour.

Although the researchers did not explicitly frame the study within the political parallelism model, the results clearly reflect patterns consistent with partisan media alignment. The link between media content and voter decision making points to institutional loyalties embedded within editorial practices. This reveals the tendency of media organisations to reinforce political biases, a hallmark of political parallelism. The researchers recommended that journalists exercise professional caution in political reporting, especially during elections. They emphasised that ethical journalism and balanced framing are essential to safeguarding voter autonomy and democratic integrity.

Skjerdal (2012) in a study titled "*Media Ethics and the State: A Study of Media Systems in Sub-Saharan Africa*," explored the structure and function of media systems across multiple African countries, including Nigeria. Drawing on interviews with journalists and content analysis of major national newspapers, the study revealed entrenched patterns of editorial bias and political selectivity. In the Nigerian context, Skjerdal observed that media ownership structures, financial dependencies on political advertisers, and internal newsroom cultures contribute significantly to partisan reporting. These dynamics were found to align the media with dominant political actors, especially during election periods, thereby reinforcing the phenomenon of political parallelism.

The study provides substantial support for the current paper's focus on the role of media alignment in shaping electoral choices. It underscores how media institutions in

Nigeria often act as instruments of elite political interests rather than as independent channels for public enlightenment. Skjerdal's work affirms that political parallelism in the Nigerian media space is structurally embedded and routinely affects the diversity and neutrality of electoral information accessible to voters.

However, a point of divergence arises from the study's analytical emphasis. While Skjerdal focused primarily on the structural and institutional drivers of political alignment in media systems, the current paper extends the discourse by interrogating how such alignments influence voters' choices in actual electoral settings. Unlike Skjerdal, who does not examine electoral behaviour outcomes directly, this paper considers how editorial bias, media partisanship, and content slant translate into real-world voter decisions, especially in contexts of competitive elections where media narratives heavily frame candidate appeal and issue salience.

Methodology

This paper adopted a qualitative approach rooted in critical analysis of published literature and empirical studies relevant to political parallelism and electoral decision-making. Rather than generating new field data, it engaged existing scholarly works to examine how partisan media structures influence voters' choices during elections in Nigeria. Published studies, journal articles and theoretical expositions were reviewed, with particular focus on works addressing media ownership, editorial alignment and the partisan framing of political content. Sources were selected based on thematic relevance and credibility, with more preference given to works from 2010 onwards to reflect current realities. The analysis draws from comparative and context-specific literature to assess how media institutions shape electoral choices through selective reporting and ideological alignment. By synthesising verified research evidence, the paper constructs a position on the impact of political parallelism on voters' choice, especially within Nigeria's competitive election environment.

Discussion

Political parallelism poses a profound challenge to the integrity of electoral choice in Nigeria. Rather than acting as a neutral platform for democratic deliberation, the media have increasingly become conduits for advancing partisan interests. The entrenchment of political affiliations within media ownership and editorial practice ensures that content is rarely dispassionate. This condition undermines the ideal of informed choice, as voters are routinely exposed to coverage that is not merely selective but structurally aligned with dominant political narratives.

Structural analyses by Hallin & Mancini (2004) and Olorunnisola & Adegoke (2020) confirm that political affiliations often determine editorial direction. However, the deeper consequence lies in the cumulative effect such biased coverage has on electoral reasoning. When voters are presented with narratives that prioritise certain candidates while sidelining others, democratic participation becomes a function of exposure, not conviction. The problem is no longer simply about media bias, but about the gradual erosion of voter autonomy through consistent exposure to ideologically loaded content.

The study by Ndubuisi, Ogunyemi & Enabunene (2022) illustrates that candidate framing significantly influenced voter preference in the 2020 Edo State election. Similarly, Skjerdal (2012) revealed how ownership, advertising structures, and newsroom culture collectively skew content in favour of elite interests. These findings establish the operational reality of political parallelism. Yet, beyond these empirical illustrations, there is a need to recognise how media systems actively construct the boundaries within which political choices are made. Voters are not merely reacting to news; they are being oriented through it.

This dynamic becomes even more complex with the influence of digital platforms. While online media theoretically allow for greater diversity of expression, they often replicate the same partisan filters found in traditional spaces. The unregulated nature of these platforms creates an environment in which misinformation thrives and editorial slants are amplified without institutional checks. Consequently, the media environment is saturated with content that reinforces existing loyalties rather than challenging them.

Political choices in such a context are frequently the outcome of engineered exposure rather than informed deliberation. Repeated partisan messaging, especially in a media ecosystem dominated by political affiliations, narrows the intellectual space for reflection. Visibility becomes equated with credibility and popularity with competence. This distortion compromises electoral competition and stifles democratic accountability. Restoring the integrity of electoral choice requires more than technical regulation. It demands a fundamental shift in the normative expectations placed on media institutions and a corresponding elevation of citizens' capacity for critical engagement. Without confronting the mechanisms through which political parallelism shapes voter behaviour, elections risk becoming ritualistic affirmations of media-projected outcomes, rather than genuine expressions of collective will.

Conclusion

The reality of political parallelism in Nigeria's media landscape presents a formidable challenge to the democratic promise of electoral choice. As this paper has demonstrated, media institutions often operate not as impartial conduits of public information but as extensions of political alliances, reinforcing the visibility and legitimacy of select candidates while marginalising others. This structural alignment, rooted in ownership patterns and editorial practices, significantly influences how voters access and interpret political information during election periods. The consequences are not trivial. A democracy that fails to guarantee an open, pluralistic, and balanced media environment risks reducing elections to contests of media amplification rather than contests of ideas. As long as political parallelism remains entrenched, the electorate will continue to make choices within a constrained informational space, vulnerable to manipulation and distortion.

To redress this situation, a number of recommendations are essential; first, there must be deliberate efforts to reform the structure of media ownership in Nigeria, promoting diversity and reducing direct political control of editorial boards. Regulatory

institutions such as the Nigerian Broadcasting Commission must be strengthened to enforce professional standards consistently and without fear or favour. Additionally, media literacy programmes should be widely implemented, especially targeting first-time voters and youth demographics, to empower citizens to critically engage with political content regardless of the platform through which it is delivered.

Media organisations themselves must recommit to professional autonomy, editorial fairness, and ethical journalism. While ideological leanings may be inevitable in any political society, the press must draw a clear line between political affiliation and journalistic duty. Where this line is deliberately blurred, the result is not civic enlightenment but democratic corrosion.

Finally, scholars and researchers must continue to give political parallelism the analytical attention it deserves. Unlike more extensively studied media concepts, political parallelism remains underexplored within Nigerian academic discourse. As a framework, it offers a valuable lens for understanding the interplay between political institutions and media behaviour. Without sustained scholarly engagement, the normative assumptions of media neutrality will persist unchallenged, and the role of the press in shaping voter choices will remain obscured.

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